

PEĐAGOGIK VA PSIXOLOGIK TADQIQOTLAR

ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ И ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL STUDIES

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GENERAL ANALYSIS OF THE PSYCHOLOGICAL STATE OF PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES

ANNOTATION

This article emphasizes the general psychological conditions of people with disabilities, the psychological problems they face, and the relevance of working on them. The article also attempts to scientifically substantiate the psychological conditions they reported during interviews with some people with disabilities for the purpose of research.

Key words: disability, psychology, social anxiety, effectiveness, hearing, vision, memory, art therapy, "inferiority complex".

ОБЩИЙ АНАЛИЗ ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО СОСТОЯНИЯ ЛЮДЕЙ С ОГРАНИЧЕННЫМИ ВОЗМОЖНОСТЯМИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье особое внимание уделяется общему психологическому состоянию людей с ограниченными возможностями, психологическим проблемам, с которыми они сталкиваются, и актуальности работы над ними. В статье также предпринята попытка научно обосновать психологические состояния, о которых они сообщали в ходе интервью с некоторыми людьми с ограниченными возможностями в целях исследования.

Ключевые слова: инвалидность, психология, социальная тревожность, эффективность, слух, зрение, память, арт-терапия, "комплекс неполноценности".

ПСИХОЛОГИК ҲОЛАТИНИГ УМУМИЙ ТАҲЛИЛИ НОГИРОНЛАРНИНГ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Ушбу мақолада ногиронларнинг умумий психологик шароитлари, улар дуч келадиган психологик муаммолар ва улар устида ишлашнинг долзарблиги таъкидланган. Мақола, шунингдек, тадқиқот мақсадида баъзи ногиронлар билан суҳбатлар пайтида улар хабар берган психологик шароитларни илмий асослашга ҳаракат қилади.

Калит сўзлар: ногиронлик, психология, ижтимоий ташвиш, самарадорлик, ешитиш, кўриш, хотира, арт-терапия, "пастлик комплекси".

INTRODUCTION

Various measures and reforms are constantly being implemented in our country to protect the interests of persons with disabilities and to recognize them as full members of our society. In particular, the signing of the Decree "On Measures to Radically Improve the System of State Support for Persons with Disabilities" by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev on December 1, 2017 is a clear proof that our state is pursuing a strong and targeted social protection policy [1].

In addition, in the Address to the Oliy Majlis of the President of our country Shavkat Mirziyoyev on January 24, 2020, important tasks were highlighted, including the need to "introduce a separate system of working with citizens with disabilities, gradually transition to a "social model" of determining disability in accordance with world standards, and introduce a new system for providing the needy population with prosthetic and orthopedic products and rehabilitation tools" [2].

In addition, in order to develop inclusive education in Uzbekistan, improve the system of education and upbringing of children with special educational needs, and improve the quality of educational services provided to them, a concept for the development of inclusive education in the public education system for 2020-2025 has been developed. At the videoconference meeting chaired by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev on December 13, 2024, to discuss the effectiveness of work in the field of social protection and priority tasks for 2025, the attention that is and should be given to persons with disabilities and those in need of social protection, as well as the measures being taken in this regard, was also discussed. Accordingly, persons with disabilities in society are entitled to comprehensive support, attention, and rights.

The success of a person with disabilities in their relationships with people around them has a significant impact on him. A person should feel comfortable. It is important to take into account the state of a person at a certain time. Studying the psychological state of a person with a problem plays a particularly important role in creating positive situations. From this point of view, studying the psychological state of people with one or another form of disability and conducting research on them will have a positive effect on solving the problems that people with disabilities may encounter, as well as on their integration into society and social adaptation.

METHODOLOGY

In the article, the author refers to the works of E. Erikson, A. Bandura, L. S. Vygotsky and others on the psychology of personality. He also refers to the works of such scientists in our country as Sagatova Sh. F., Rashidov O. S., scientists who did research on the general condition of people with disabilities, their specific characteristics. It is no secret that the ability to feel one's true self plays an important role in the psyche of every person. According to E. Erikson, identification is a socialized part of our identity.

Each society is a repertoire of characteristics: from the personality of a child, father, mother, to professional, political and other characteristics. Some invisible lottery distributes and assigns them to different individuals. Some of them are assigned to us from birth, only in a slightly changed state (gender, race); others later, of their own free will, encounter an entrepreneur, farmer or engineer, taxpayer or criminal, and other forms of personality. We accept them in relationships with others who define and identify us. Only when others affirm a person is this true for him or her. [3, P.12].

Based on this idea, the most important aspect of working with the psychology of a student with a disability is to help him or her first feel his or her own identity.

A. Bandura emphasized that self-efficacy determines a person's determination to act in the face of obstacles and unpleasant experiences and influences their efforts to overcome difficulties [4].

In his opinion, self-efficacy is a central and important determinant of human behavior, allowing them to correctly predict their actual actions. In his social cognitive theory of learning, self-efficacy is presented as an important factor that affects human behavior and its results through cognitive, motivational, affective and physiological processes. Accordingly, achieving self-efficacy is the next task in working with the psyche of a student with disabilities.

According to L. S. Vygotsky, the main fact that specialists encounter in the development complicated by defects is the two-sided role of the organic defect in the process of development and in the formation of the child's personality. On the one hand, the defect is a minus, a limitation, a weakness, a slowdown in development; on the other hand, precisely because it causes difficulties, it stimulates an increasing, intensified forward movement. [5.c-3]. Accordingly, any defect is an impetus for another specific development.

According to O.Rashidov, it is appropriate to develop the educational system taking into account the specific aspects of each nation and people, national traditions, customs, goals and tasks of the state, and mental and physical development of students. In the case of children with disabilities, if adults do not oppose the child's opinion and independence, but help the child's wishes and aspirations as much as possible, the difficulties in the process of forming his personality will disappear by themselves. Stubbornness, obstinacy, and disobedience appear in a child with limited abilities as a result of excessive petting by adults [6]. Accordingly, the correct approach of adults, parents and educators plays an important role in the positive formation of the psyche of children with special education needs.

According to Sh. Sagatova, as soon as a child with a developmental disability is born in a family, the psychological environment, interpersonal relationships, values, and in general, the family is destroyed from within, and this situation cannot but have a negative impact on the physical and mental development of the disabled child [7]. In addition, there are many families that do not want to register their disabled child. They say or worry about bureaucratic obstacles. Because there is discrimination in our society. Even in education, if a child from a family whose disability group is not determined and is not officially registered, there may be problems with placement in a special boarding school, and they may not receive disability benefits. Accordingly, we can say that society needs not only assistance measures and psychological support for a person with a disability, but also necessary support measures for his parents.

MAIN PART

Human life is very fragile. In the course of life, each citizen may face various risks that can directly affect his health and ability to work. Among these risks, we can include being born with a disability or becoming disabled due to an accident. In most cases, a person cannot overcome these situations on his own, since they are largely determined by objective socio-economic living conditions. Until recently, ideas about the psychology of disability were developed only by non-disabled people and almost always in rehabilitation or medical institutions. In general, these interpreters of the psychology of disability were able-bodied practitioners (doctors or therapists) who worked with disabled adults or, more often, disabled children and their able-bodied parents. It is necessary to try to ensure that the disabled person does not feel dependent on you.

It is important to communicate with him on an equal footing, but at the same time, providing him with the necessary practical assistance leads to the formation of a system between speech connections and speech. Excessive interest in his characteristics, as well as sympathy, can reduce his interest in communication. It should be remembered that the first task that can be given to positive help is to create a basis for the student to change, feel good about himself and be ready to become independent.

Let's talk about the general psychological characteristics of people with hearing and vision impairment;

Features specific to people with hearing impairments:

The peculiarities of the development of attention and perception in people with hearing impairments have a significant impact on memory activity. Visual perception predominates in them, therefore the entire memorization process is based mainly on visual images, while for hearing people this process is auditory-visual and relies on active speech. In connection with hearing impairments, vision plays a special role, on the basis of which the speech of a deaf child develops. In the process of knowing the world around him, instrumental, tactile and tactile-vibrational sensations are of great importance.

The memory of deaf and hard-of-hearing people has a number of specific features. Imagination changes noticeably more strongly than in people with normal hearing. On the basis of oral speech disorders, written speech disorders arise, which manifest themselves in the form of various dysgraphia and agrammatism. In cases of complete loss of hearing, speech is formed only under special training conditions and with the help of auxiliary forms - facial expressions, sign language, finger writing, lip reading. Hearing people master a large part of their social experience on their own, while people with hearing impairments have limited opportunities in this regard. Therefore, sometimes there are difficulties in communication and peculiarities in relationships, isolation.

Psychological characteristics of people with visual impairments

Vision is the most powerful source of information about the outside world. 85-90% of information enters the brain through the visual analyzer, and partial or profound disruption of its functions causes a number of deviations in the physical and mental development of a person. The visual analyzer ensures the performance of complex visual functions. It is customary to distinguish five main visual functions:

- 1) central vision;
- 2) peripheral vision;
- 3) binocular vision;
- 4) light perception;
- 5) color perception.

Poor vision impairs voluntary attention. A decrease in voluntary attention results from a violation of the emotional-volitional sphere and causes such unpleasant symptoms as a low volume of attention, disorganization, i.e., lack of purposefulness, switching from one type of activity to another or, conversely, a low level of attention switching. Defects in the visual analyzer disrupt the relationship between the main processes of excitation and inhibition, negatively affecting the speed of memorization.

Rapid forgetting of the studied material is explained not only by insufficient or absent repetition, but also by the insignificance of objects and concepts that determine them, from which people with visual impairments can only acquire verbal knowledge. The role of verbal-logical memory is enhanced in people with visual impairments. Poor retention of visual images and a decrease in the volume of long-term memory have been identified. The volume of short-term auditory memory is high in all categories of people with visual impairments.

According to L.S. Vygotsky, it was previously believed that the entire life and development of a blind child is built along the line of blindness; according to the new law, development is contrary to this line. If he is blind, then mental development is directed from blindness, against blindness. Accordingly, it is possible that the intellectual development of a blind student will be the same as that of a healthy student, and even higher [5, P.4].

Depending on the degree of damage to visual functions, the integrity of perception is disrupted. Visual-motor-auditory perception predominates in the blind. They can perceive one or two movements or separate elements of movements at the same time. The process of recognizing colored, contoured and silhouetted images by people with impaired vision is not simple. Of all types of images, colored pictures are the easiest to recognize, because color provides additional information to the shape of the images. The more complex the shape of an object and the less it resembles geometric shapes, the more difficult it is for them to recognize the object. The success of recognition in perceiving contour images depends on the clarity, contrast, and thickness of the line. Thus, children perceive lines 1.5 mm thick and drawn in black on a white background most quickly.

People with some form of disability experience increased anxiety and worry. In the psychological dictionary, anxiety is considered an individual psychological characteristic that manifests itself in a person's tendency to frequent and intense worry, as well as a temperamental characteristic that results from a low threshold for its occurrence or from the weakness of nervous processes [8, P.672].

According to a number of scientists and psychologists, most children with disabilities experience anxiety because they have difficulties in physical activity, establishing social relationships, and also misunderstanding given instructions and commands. For example, high levels of anxiety in children with cerebral palsy are associated with limited mobility and frequent hospitalizations. Children with severe speech impairments also experience increased anxiety because they do not understand spoken language and have difficulty expressing their thoughts. Anxiety in children with visual impairments is often associated with the manifestation of various fears (fear of the unknown, fear of unfamiliar spaces, etc.), and impaired interpersonal relationships with people around them.

Deaf and hard of hearing children experience anxiety in various social situations. Children with intellectual disabilities are characterized by unmotivated anxiety states. [9-c-528] In psychology, the most effective methods for correcting anxiety are recognized as various types of art therapy, for example, art therapy, fairy tale therapy, play therapy, etc. Art therapy is a method of treating nervous and mental illnesses through art and self-expression in art. During this creative period, the child overcomes his fears, complexes, experiences, and establishes relationships with others. For the not yet fully developed psyche of young people with any disabilities, the whole process occurs delicately and painlessly. Thus, the child relaxes, calms down, and therefore achieves inner harmony.

Another psychological condition that some people with some form of disability experience is a feeling of loneliness. Loneliness, which arises from emotional isolation, occurs due to a lack of attachment to a specific person or because a person separates their feelings from the memory of the event and is unable to have close relationships with others. Overcoming loneliness is a long-term process, which is associated with a person's desire to change the state of psychological needs. During the study, we interviewed members of the Tashkent city "SHAROIT PLUS" public association (NGO) of the disabled. During the interview, the chairman of the association, M. Rakhimova (52 years old, disabled person of group I), shared her experiences.

"I couldn't go to school because of my physical disability, and I had to stay home because my parents couldn't take me to clubs or groups where I could have people like me. The most memorable feeling from that time was how lonely I was. I thought there were no other people like me in the world," recalls Muhabbat. Later, when she joined a disability organization and began to communicate with people like her, our heroine notes that this feeling of isolation often had a negative impact on her socialization with her peers.

The next important socio-psychological problem is the problem of social depression. Frustration (from Latin frustratio - deception, vain expectation) is a mental state that arises as a result of the inability to satisfy a need or desire. It appears in a conflicting situation, for example, when meeting insurmountable or difficult obstacles to satisfying a need, and when various negative experiences are accompanied by hopelessness, nervousness, anxiety, etc. Our next hero M. Egamov (27 years old, disabled person of group I) says that his mental state before joining his teammates was depression, and this problem still bothers him. "Because of my physical condition, I am always forced to walk on my knees. When I see my healthy peers, I envy them. Even if I accept this condition as much as possible, I get depressed thinking that it will be more difficult to walk on my knees as I get older," says our hero.

Disability is destructive. Limited life activities and uncertainty about the future make a disabled person feel hopeless and often lead to a depletion of mental strength. Some blame themselves for everything, others blame external circumstances, others endure a state of hopelessness, and still others are ready to actively influence these circumstances and want to change them.

Among our interlocutors is a student with visual impairment - M. Jurabayeva (22 years old, disabled person of group II). Despite her problems, M., who is studying medicine, is trying hard to find her place in life. Not to lag behind her healthy peers is her most important goal, she has managed to become a student of a prestigious university, and she speaks English fluently.

While answering questions, it was possible to notice that the girl's mood changes very quickly. She herself admitted that emotional instability is a consequence of her certain medical condition. It turned out that she tries to hide the depression that always accompanies her by talking loudly, often, and trying to look cheerful. Our girl's feeling of self-satisfaction and self-motivation for perfection are reflected in the "inferiority complex" put forward by A. Adler in science. Adler believed that this emotional state was beneficial for self-improvement. Adler argued that feelings of dissatisfaction with oneself motivated a person to strive for superiority and success [10].

Based on such analysis, teachers who provide education to persons with any form of disability

RECOMMENDATIONS

In teaching hearing impaired people:

Trying to make a short pause after explaining any question; Using visual material as much as possible;

Always looking at the person with hearing loss when talking to him/her;

Being friendly to the person you are talking to, not showing displeasure or anger when they do not understand your speech;

Learning how to quickly help him/her during a conversation or lesson: - repeating the phrase at a slower pace with the same word order;

Recording lectures on video, using captions on the screen, showing slides and tapes using computer training programs; They can also be accompanied by text messages and light signals when events occur on the computer screen. In addition, hearing-impaired students can use hearing aids to amplify the sound.

In teaching visually impaired people:

The workplace of a student with visual impairment should be located in the first or second row. It is advisable to equip it with additional lighting. It is recommended that a teacher working with such a student not stand in the room facing the light or the window. Since the speed of work of people with visual impairment is slower, more time should be given to complete tasks (especially written tasks). Visual material should be large, clearly visible in color, contours, silhouettes and correspond to natural dimensions. The time allocated for completing tasks should be increased.

CONCLUSION

Every person deserves respect and encouragement. The presence of a disability, no matter how serious it may be, does not alter fundamental rights. People, regardless of their age or their life expectancy, have the right to enrich their lives and develop their abilities. A person should not be made to feel inferior or give up hope. A person should not be forgotten or deprived. Grouping people by a particular disability should not lead to stereotypical conclusions about them. The differences in the needs, abilities and circumstances of people with the same or similar disabilities require diversification.

In this regard, working primarily on their mental state will yield positive results. Accordingly, we believe that it is necessary to establish special psychological support networks for people with disabilities and their parents, and to improve the quality of existing ones. In addition, representatives of other sectors of public cooperation should also pay special attention to this problem. In particular, it would be correct to say that the activities of state and non-governmental organizations in the implementation of their tasks related to persons with disabilities should be approached with special attention in the adoption of regulatory documents, and to give their opinions and recommendations. For this, the targeted allocation of funds allocated to persons with disabilities, social grant projects and amounts financed with the help of other sponsors is important not only for the social adaptation of persons with disabilities, but also for the positive solution of their psychological problems in life. Only then can we see the results and fruits of the work done. In addition, although research on the mental state of persons with disabilities exists in our country, it is not enough, so it is advisable to conduct more research.

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